

Experimental evaluation of the effectiveness of materials in a porous fired clay wall evaporative water cooling system

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Abstract - Evaporative cooling through porous materials is a passive, energy-efficient, and environmentally friendly technique for preserving water and food in hot, dry climates. This study comparatively evaluates the thermal and hygrometric efficiency of different stands composed of two fired jars placed one inside the other, separated by porous materials (sand, cotton fabric, cloth) in the cooling of water by evaporation. Experimental tests were conducted on jars of identical geometry, filled with water and exposed to identical atmospheric conditions. The parameters measured were water temperature, ambient temperature, relative humidity, and wind speed. The lowest (minimum) water temperature, 16.32°C for all variants, was observed on December 26, 2025, when the relative humidity had dropped to 45% with an ambient temperature of 27.55°C; on that day, the wind speed was slightly high at 20 km/h. The maximum values of 25.51°C for the jar with fabric and 26.53°C for the other two were observed on January 7, with a relative humidity of 81% and an ambient temperature of 27.55°C. So we proposed a system consisting of cotton fabric followed by sand and finally a cloth to achieve the desired cooling effect. However, it should be noted that from a durability perspective, cotton fabric will not withstand constant moisture.

Keywords - Comparative, efficiency, porous materials, fired clay, cooling, evaporation

I. INTRODUCTION

Evaporative cooling of water through materials plays an essential role in many areas, including industry, energy production, and air conditioning systems. The efficiency of this process depends largely on the materials used in the installations, as they influence heat transfer, corrosion resistance, and equipment durability. Thus, the choice of materials is a determining factor in ensuring performance, safety, and energy savings [1]. It should be noted that population growth and technological development, combined with the quest for thermal comfort, mean that appliances such as air conditioners and refrigerators are becoming more commonplace every day, thereby increasing energy demand. However, these appliances are a major contributor to pollution and increased greenhouse gas emissions [2].

This is why, in a context of global warming and increasingly scarce energy resources, the search for

passive solutions for cooling and preserving food products has become a major challenge, particularly in rural areas of developing countries [3]. Evaporative cooling using porous materials, such as fired clay jars or double jar systems, offers a simple, environmentally friendly, and inexpensive alternative to mechanical refrigeration systems [4][5].

Over the past few decades, legislation has tightened standards relating to thermal comfort and energy efficiency in new buildings, while encouraging renovation initiatives aimed at optimizing the performance of existing buildings [6]. Furthermore, rapid urbanization and the digitization of everyday life are creating a multitude of opportunities for users, positioning buildings as crucial elements of the energy system thanks to their ability to generate green energy and adjust consumption over time [7]. The principle is based on the evaporation of water from the outer surface of the porous container (fired clay jars). This evaporation consumes latent heat, which lowers the

temperature of the water contained in the container [8]. The effectiveness of the process depends heavily on the nature of the material, its porosity, its water retention capacity, the ambient temperature, relative humidity, and air velocity [9]. Numerous studies have explored the behavior of fired clay, but few have systematically compared the effectiveness of fired clay jars with other natural or composite materials in the same experimental context [10][11].

With a view to evaluating and improving the performance of Tunisian clay ceramic products in the Bir Mcherga region [12][13], clay was mixed with non-plastic minerals such as sand, brick waste, and chamotte in order to optimize the manufacturing process and improve the quality of the finished products. In studying the thermal performance of a local refrigerator based on water evaporation through a porous fired clay wall, [14] designed, simulated, and tested a refrigerator consisting of two jars and a layer of sand in order to optimize the parameters (temperature, relative humidity, and total exchange surface area) that could influence its operation and minimize the amount of water to be evaporated. In this study, the results showed that the water temperature in the refrigerator cannot be lowered below the wet bulb temperature of the evaporator air. In the experimental analysis of evaporative cooling of water in porous clay containers under different environmental conditions, [15][16] stored water in six (6) containers of different sizes and volumes. The weight, relative humidity, and ambient temperature of the water contained in the containers were measured every two hours, from noon to 8 p.m., for seven days.

The results they obtained revealed that mass loss is influenced by several factors, such as ambient temperature, container surface area, porosity, and thickness. This study showed that the pots with the smallest capacity (pots D and E) experienced the fastest evaporation rate [17] determined the thermal behavior of the dual-storage refrigerator and developed a two-dimensional unsteady mathematical model of a terracotta pot refrigerator, validated by experimental results obtained in a climate chamber. Tests conducted at different relative humidity levels and dry temperatures, and their results, made it possible to determine the pot's efficiency, its coefficient of performance (COP), and the variation of other parameters depending on ambient conditions. In evaluating the transient performance of a porous evaporative cooler for fruit and vegetable storage, [18][19] determined the performance of the evaporative cooler during four periods of the year, covering Nigeria's two main climatic seasons. The results showed a reduction in the storage chamber

temperature of up to 9°C compared to the ambient temperature, which ranged between 22 and 33°C.

They specified that optimal performance was observed during the dry season. From all of the above, we understand that a great deal of work has been done in the field of evaporative cooling through porous media, but none of this work has focused on comparing the cooling efficiency of different materials, which is the objective of our study in this article, starting with porous materials with identical wall thicknesses and geometries and under the same climatic conditions.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

2.1.1. Description of the study area

Mamou, the study area is located 270 km from the capital Conakry, in the south of the Fouta-Djallon central massif between 10° 22.53' north latitude and 12° 5.48' west longitude. The prefecture of Mamou covers an area of 8,674.32 km² with an altitude of 720 m above sea level. The relief and altitude of Fouta are the main factors influencing the climate. Like Guinea in general, Mamou has a tropical (or Fouta) climate, characterized by two alternating seasons: a dry season (November to April) and a rainy season (May to October). The harmattan wind is felt during the dry season, and the humidity level easily drops below 45%. Rainfall is very abundant, with an average annual rainfall of 2,087 mm [20]. As for winds other than the Harmattan and monsoon, which are dominant at ground level, mountain and valley breezes blow steadily.

The average monthly temperatures in Mamou range from 21°C to 29°C. The highest maximum temperatures are observed in March and April, with average temperatures sometimes reaching 37°C, while the lowest minimum temperatures, averaging around 11°C, are recorded in December. Relative humidity reaches around 87% in August and the average wind speed is around 2.92 m/s [21]. In such conditions, the atmosphere is hot and the relative humidity is high, which limits the effect of evaporation. However, it can be enhanced by using methods such as assembling two nested jars with highly porous substances placed between them. By inserting one jar into another larger one with porous material in between, the efficiency of the evaporation process is optimized through cooling.

2.1.2. Materials studied

The materials used to make these devices fall into two (2) categories:

a) **Manufacturing materials:** Four types of materials were selected

- Fired clay : a traditional material used to make water jars.
- Sand : Granules obtained by crushing sand, fragments of rock with multiple uses: concrete production, backfill, etc.
- Cotton fabric: Known for its softness, breathability, and durability, cotton is used in a multitude of projects, ranging from clothing to interior decoration items.
- Cloth: Composed of open cells, which make it a naturally ventilated foam and allow water to drain through these cells.

Each material was used to make a stand consisting of two fired clay jars with either a layer of sand, a layer of cotton fabric, or a layer of cloth between them. These materials were collected in the prefecture of Siguiri, an administrative subdivision of the Kankan region located 761 km from Conakry (capital of the Republic of Guinea), and transported to the energy systems laboratory at the Higher Institute of Technology in Mamou.

b) **Measuring instruments**

- KRYSTAL MY-64 thermocouple multimeter : A device for measuring temperature, consisting of two wires of different metals connected at each end. One junction is placed where the temperature is to be measured, and the other is kept at a constant lower temperature.
- Ruler graduated in centimeters for measuring and gauging the water level in the jar
- Thermo-hygrometer : Portable temperature and humidity measuring device (thermohygrometer), Rotronic DV-2 type. Humidity is measured using a capacitive sensor, temperature using a silicon diode.

2.2. Method

The method used in this study focuses on the sizing, production, and comparison of fired clay jars made from different materials.

2.2.1. Production

To make the jars, we collected clay from a quarry often used by local potters. After crushing, we sifted the clay to remove solid particles, plant debris, and roots. We then gradually added water to the powder and kneaded it for about 30 minutes until we obtained a smooth paste without air bubbles. Using pottery molds, we made jars of different sizes so that they could be stacked inside each other with space between them. These jars were stored for 24 hours under plastic to prevent cracks, then dried in the sun for five days before being fired in a traditional 900°C kiln. Diagram showing how to make jars.

The different parameters of the jars are shown in Table 1:

Table 1 The different parameters of the jars

N°	Parameters	Values
1	Thickness (inner and outer jars)	1.9 cm
2	Diameter of the inner jar opening	20 cm
3	Diameter of the outer jar opening	33 cm
4	Space between inner and outer jars (thickness of material layers)	3 cm
5	Volume of the inner jar	10 L
6	Volume of the outer jar	12 L

2.2.2 Testing the device

As part of testing and comparing our devices, we set up our jars under a tree in the courtyard of the Mamou Higher Institute of Technology, then filled the space between the two jars with sand, cotton fabric, and rags. Finally, we filled each of the inner jars with 10 liters of tap water. It should be noted that the tap water, clay, sand, cotton fabric, and cloth used were not analyzed in a laboratory. The materials placed between the jars were watered every two days during the experiment.

These figures show some images of the stands.

Figure 1 Experimental setups

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Terracotta or clay materials have always been used by certain rural populations in Africa and around the world as a method of preserving foodstuffs through a system of direct or indirect evaporative cooling [22][23][24]. Another seed preservation technique was developed by [25] using PICS (Purdue Improved Crop Storage) bags and plastic jars. For this study, we designed an evaporative cooling device using a porous material (clay jar), which is a passive, energy-efficient technique with minimal environmental impact, intended for the preservation of water and food in hot and dry climates. To do this, we conducted

a comparative assessment of the thermal and hygrometric efficiency of different stands composed of two fired jars, one placed inside the other, with porous materials (sand, cotton fabric, cloth) in between, with the aim of cooling the water through evaporation. In order to provide a clear reading of the variation in water temperature in the jars over time, we have represented the different results in graphs according to each operating condition.

The temperature curves for the water in the jars, the ambient air, and the relative humidity obtained from measurements taken between December 21, 2025, and January 19, 2026, are shown in graphs 3, 4, and 5.

Figure 3 Variation in water temperature, air temperature, and relative humidity over time in jars lined with cotton fabric

Figure 4 Variation in water temperature, air temperature, and relative humidity over time across jars with cloth

Figure 5 Variation in water temperature, air temperature, and relative humidity over time in jars filled with sand

The experimental curves (Figures 3, 4, and 5) show roughly the same patterns. However, when we take Figure 3 as an example, we see a decrease in water temperature from the second day onwards, then the curve remains constant until the fifth day, followed by an irregular, sawtooth pattern until the tenth day, then a slight increase until the seventeenth day, followed by an increase on the eighteenth day and a decrease until the twenty-fourth day, then a slight increase until the twenty-seventh day, followed by a decrease and an increase until the thirtieth day. This may be due to unstable air humidity and wind speed. In terms of these curves, it was found that the lowest point (minimum) would be (16.32°C), obtained on the morning of December 26, 2025, between 9 a.m. and 11 a.m. However, the relative humidity had dropped

to 45% with an ambient temperature of 27.55°C and a wind speed of 20km/h. These results show that the device works well with low humidity, because the lower the humidity, the lower the temperature of the water in the jar. He noted that during the Harmattan season (November to December) in Mamou, the ambient temperature is around 19°C, wind speeds are high, and relative humidity is low. Thus, the further away from December, the lower the temperature, the higher the air temperature, and the higher the relative humidity. These weather variations are probably due to the Harmattan, which is a factor in increasing wind speed, leading to an increase in the temperature of the water in the internal jars. This increase in water temperature in the jars is irregular because the environmental parameters are unstable. To compare the performance of the materials used, we plotted curves showing the evolution of water temperature over time for the three stands on the same graph, which is shown in (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Comparison of three materials

From this graph, we can see that the curves are almost identical, but given the specific characteristics of the materials, there is still a slight difference in the shape of the curves. The cotton fabric system has a minimum value of 16.32°C and a maximum value of 27.55°C, with an average of 21.45°C, showing a slight decrease in temperature compared to the other two, followed by the sand system, which has a minimum value of 16.32°C and a maximum value of 26.53°C, with an average of 21.62°C. Once the water used to spray (drip) these materials begins to dry, the cloth heats up and prevents cooling, which is why it is last with a minimum temperature of 16.32°C and a maximum of 26.53°C, but with an average temperature of 21.74°C. Therefore, based on this, we recommend a system consisting of cotton fabric followed by sand and finally the cloth to achieve the desired cooling effect. However, it should be noted that from a durability standpoint, cotton fabric will not withstand prolonged moisture unless it is replaced on a regular basis.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this experiment, refrigeration systems based on the evaporation of water through a porous fired clay wall were designed and tested. The results we obtained showed that this phenomenon of water cooling in fired clay is strongly influenced by physical factors that mainly affect the evaporation of a liquid through a porous wall, namely: ambient air temperature, relative humidity of the ambient air, exchange surface area, wind speed, and the materials of which they are made.

The three variants tested all gave roughly the same result at times, although the cotton fabric system remained slightly better, followed by the sand system and finally the cloth system.

These refrigerators consume no electricity and can be used in many areas, such as water cooling, food preservation, and even room air conditioning.

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